

Syntactic stylistic devices

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Annotation

This article explains stylistic syntactic devices as a general syntactic type of language, analyzes syntactic stylistic procedures, and provides instances of them.

Keywords: syntactic and stylistic devices, gradation, ellipsis, inversion, parallelism.

Аннотация

В данной статье стилистические синтаксические приемы рассматриваются как общий синтаксический тип языка, анализируются синтаксические стилистические приемы и приводятся их примеры.

Ключевые слова: синтаксические и стилистические приемы, градация, многоточие, инверсия, параллелизм.

We may then infer the following conclusions from the aforementioned arguments if any modifications to the syntactic structure do not impact the content:

1. The existing material is defined by its basic elements.
2. The individual meanings of the constituent pieces are referred to as grammatical and structural meanings.
3. Lexical and textual meanings can be influenced by structural meanings. The aforementioned indicates that speech patterns are crucial in the development of thought processes.

Syntactic stylistic devices are particular applications in speech construction that are used to portray emotions and give rise to particular styles of speech. These tools are used to build unusual phrases that differ significantly from neutral syntactic units. Below, we'll look at how this "special" relates to the straightforward "neutral." Understanding the conventions of syntactic language is essential to comprehending the nature of syntactic stylistic devices. The syntactic stylistic approach is regarded as an expression of one's own judgment rather than a mistake resulting from a deviation from accepted morphological, syntactic, and stylistic principles. One general syntactic kind of a language to study is stylistic syntactic creations. Application of phonetic, morphological, syntactic, and stylistic norms of speech in many contexts is the norm. A shift in word order in the first sentence gave rise to a beautiful, romantic mood. By rearranging the words, the second sentence gives the word "affection" a different

meaning. Stated differently, these words convey the speaker's attitude. Let's contrast it with the conventional neutral assertion. Sentences take off. She yearned for affection. The meaning of the second sentence is as follows:

In relation to syntax, it's important to stress how crucial tone is to how speech is put together. Authors convey the tone of their writing through linguistic and nonlinguistic paralinguistic devices. The means of syntactic stylistic influence are by their very nature close to the features of oral speech. The excitement of the speaker can also be an important factor in the development of sensitivity. In such cases, he omitted parts of the proposal. As a result, an ellipse is used, sometimes the same word is repeated. You can change the order of words in a sentence without changing the main content of the idea expressed by the speaker. Sometimes the tuner lists and describes the causes and consequences of the event for someone using counting and gradation. Rhetorical interrogative sentences, conflicting words, etc. are often used in oral speech. As a result of changes in the structure of such proposals, additional meaning appears. Several compounds are also widely used as visual aids. All this create emphasis, emotionality and sensitivity in oral speech. However, all these means of syntactic influence are generalized, combined, perform a certain function and take the form of a stylistic environment, mainly in the style of prose.

Repetition is a stylistic tool used to express excitement. Emotional speech is characterized by brevity, logic and repetition of certain parts of the expressed thought. The repetition of certain words and whole phrases in spoken language is certain: she cried out loudly: "Where is my child? But where is my child? I want to know where my child is? In this example, repetition does not fulfill any stylistic function and expresses only a certain mental state of the speaker. Repetition is used as a stylistic tool to attract the attention of the reader.

Synonymous repetition in the speaker's speech serves to increase and convince the power of speech, to detail it in artistic speech. While speaking about synonymous repetition, it is necessary to mention the problem of pleonasm. In pleonasm, not only the same word or means is repeated, but also the same content, meaning. This seems an exaggeration; it does not add any value to the recognized opinion. Pleonasm is a speech impediment. Pleonasms are synonymous with repetition, which are not based on artistic and aesthetic considerations. However, the phenomenon of pleonasm is practically absent in the language, especially in the Uzbek language. One of the simple tasks of repetition is to influence sometimes expressing a sequence of actions. This task is performed using rhythm. Another function of repetition is to enhance the meaning of a sentence. Sometimes these things or actions are similar or close to each other, one

in a pair of the other. This method is widely used mainly in the artistic style and serves to express speech. In gradation each specific phrase in a sentence becomes stronger and more effective than its predecessor (in terms of efficiency and logic). Synonyms are often used in gradations. The reuse of these synonyms helps to discern the effect. In short, syntactic stylistic devices include inversion, indivisible structures, parallel devices, chiasm, repetition, ellipse, accent, counting, gradation, antithesis, and each of them performs a specific function.

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